

Effect of Cognitive Behavior Therapy and Motivational Interviewing on Mental Health and Life Satisfaction of Substance Users in Residential Settings

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to examine the impact of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) and Motivational Interviewing (MI) on the mental health outcomes—depression, anxiety, stress—and life satisfaction among male substance users. Specifically, the objectives were to compare pre-test scores between non-interventional and interventional groups, assess the post-intervention impact of CBT and MI, and determine its effectiveness in reducing negative mental health symptoms and enhancing life satisfaction from pre-test to post-test. The hypotheses stated that there would be no significant differences in pre-test scores between groups, but the CBT and MI interventional group would show significantly lower depression, anxiety, and stress, alongside higher life satisfaction post-intervention. A total of 60 male participants, aged 18-40, from government rehabilitation centers in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, were randomly assigned to non-interventional (n=30) and interventional (n=30) groups. The Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS-21) and Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) were used to measure outcomes. Pre-test comparisons showed no significant differences between groups. However, post-test results revealed that the interventional group had significantly lower depression (M=10.43, SD=1.96), anxiety (M=9.93, SD=2.86), and stress (M=10.63, SD=2.23), and significantly higher life satisfaction (M=19.43, SD=1.98) compared to the non-interventional group. Large effect sizes (Cohen's $d > 2.0$) indicated a strong impact of CBT on mental health and life satisfaction. These findings suggest that CBT and MI are an effective intervention for improving psychological well-being among substance users.

Keywords: Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, Motivational Interviewing, Non-Interventional Group, Interventional Group, substance users, mental health, depression, anxiety, stress, life satisfaction

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1. Introduction

Substance use and addiction are significant public health issues with far-reaching consequences that impact not only individuals but also families, communities, and national dynamics. Addiction and substance abuse are psychosocial traumas that can erode personal well-being, disrupt families, and strain societal structures, often leading to increased criminality, reduced economic productivity, and even death (Lander et al., 2013; Volkow, 2014). An illness that involves the recurrent use of drugs, drug dependence or drug addiction is defined as compulsive drug use, inability to quit using the substance, withdrawal symptoms and drug use despite adverse effects (Gupta & Kulhara, 2007). Based on the Description of dimensions of addiction the American Society of Addiction Medicine (ASAM) the hallmark of Addiction is characterized by the failure to achieve or maintain abstinence, Cravings, and impaired decision-making and impulse control (ASAM, 2011).

Substance use disorder (SUD), as defined by the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5), involves a maladaptive pattern of substance use causing significant impairment or distress over 12 months. Symptoms range from the inability to fulfill major life responsibilities to the development of tolerance and withdrawal symptoms (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). The prevalence of substance use disorders is a global concern, with reports indicating a rising trend in drug use. In 2018, an estimated 269 million people worldwide used drugs, with about 35 million experiencing substance use disorders (UNODC, 2020). Pakistan, positioned near Afghanistan, the world's largest heroin producer, faces an escalating drug crisis with 8.9 million drug users and 700 drug-related deaths daily (Reid et al., 2002; Qasim, 2015).

The comorbidity of substance use and mental health disorders is well-established. Substance abuse often leads to or exacerbates psychological issues, including anxiety, depression, and stress (Asselmann et al., 2014; WHO, 2010). Research shows that up to 90% of substance abusers experience mood disorders such as anxiety and depression (Hanter et al., 2013), while life satisfaction is significantly lower among substance users compared to non-users (Nargiso et al., 2015; Tang et al., 2020). Alcohol and drug consumption are also detrimental to one's social, academic and interpersonal Performances thus exacerbating the mental Wellness situation (Grant et al., 2004). The data shows that depression and anxiety along with other mental ailments coexist with the substance use and the addiction forms a vicious cycle where substance use is both a coping mechanism as well as a problem.

Other psychiatric disorders such as depression, anxiety, and stress are other related disorders in people with SUDs. Depression, for instance is a major complication which present in more than half of the drug users seeking treatment, 55% of whom are said to be suffering from clinical level of depression (Torrens et al., 2011). Anxiety is similarly common: people with SUDs have an overall one-point three times higher risk than the general population. 7 to 2. 8 times more likely to develop anxiety disorders; (Grant et al., 2004). Stress too plays a role in the onset and the relapse of the addiction, by indicating that stressor life events lead to the use of substances and aggravation of the effects (Schwabe et al., 2011). In addition, substance use decreases life satisfaction in general as

substance abusers usually suffer from poor well-being and decrease the interest of engagement in life activities that are meaningful (Bizzarri et al., 2007).

There are two well-known evidence-based therapies that can be used effectively to enhance mental health and quality of life among substance dependent patients in residential rehabilitation programs; these are CBT and MI (Jhanjee 2014). Both therapies are applied with intention of helping clients who are struggling with substance use disorder, by focusing on psychological and behavioral mechanism that lead to substance use while helping some clients to have better mental health (Hayes & Levin, 2012). CBT is targeted at making an individual change his/her thoughts and behavior which are related to substance use and co morbidity mental disorders such as anxiety and depression (Harrison et al., 2007). MI, on the other hand, employs client centered approach to address issues related with motivation and ambivalence about behaviour change, creating a therapeutic partnership where the clients work with the clinician to increase their motivation and find ways of coping (Hettema et al., 2005; Miller & Rollnick, 2012). Studies suggest that integrating CBT and MI can result in enhanced levels of treatment compliance and favourable alterations in clients' perceived standard of living (Baker et al., 2005; Burke et al., 2003). These integrated treatment modality in residential rehabilitation setting assist patient in using appropriate coping strategies on factors that triggers or stresses based on substance use hence reducing anxiety, depression, and stress thus improving quality of life (Rubak et al., 2005; Hettema et al., 2005; Jhanjee, 2014).

Numerous qualitative and quantitative studies have been carried out globally on the effectiveness of CBT and MI in the treatment of SUDs and the related psychiatric disorders. Literature on the effectiveness of CBT with substance users in western nations has revealed that CBT is effective in reducing depressive, anxious and stressed with improved satisfaction with life (McHugh et al., 2010; Riper et al., 2014; Toneatto & Calderwood, 2015). Likewise, MI has been found to be useful in increasing clients' motivation to change, in addressing ambiguity concerning change processes, and in promoting a positive therapeutic working alliance that may lead to increased engagement with treatment and even better mental health (Hettema et al., 2005; Miller & Rollnick, 2012). However, in Pakistan, despite the alarming rates of drug addiction and the clear need for effective treatment interventions, there is a noticeable lack of empirical research focused on the use of CBT and MI within the local context. While studies in Pakistan have primarily focused on the demographic and clinical profiles of individuals with substance use disorders (SUDs) without investigating the effects of CBT and MI on this population (Alavi et al., 2021; Azad et al., 2022), research on the impact of MI remains scarce as well. Some studies have explored the use of CBT in other contexts, such as its impact on individuals living with AIDS (Abbas et al., 2023), particularly in residential settings, there is even less research available on the effectiveness of specifically MI. Another study has investigated the utility of CBT in other contexts, for example the consequence of CBT on people with AIDS (Abbas et al., 2023) especially in the residential facilities; however, there is limited comparing study investigating the influence of CBT and MI on self-report psychiatric health and life satisfaction of substance users in Pakistan.

This study aims to explore the effects of CBT and MI on depression, anxiety, stress and life satisfaction of substance users in a residential setting. By examining the impact of

CBT and MI on key psychological variables such as depression, anxiety, stress, and life satisfaction, the research seeks to provide evidence of their efficacy as therapeutic interventions for substance use disorders. With the rising prevalence of substance use and its profound impact on mental health, interventions like CBT and MI hold great promise for improving the psychological wellbeing of substance users struggling with addiction.

2. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study is grounded in both CBT and MI, which together provide a comprehensive approach to addressing substance use disorders. CBT posits that maladaptive thoughts and beliefs contribute to unhealthy behaviors, such as substance abuse, by reinforcing negative emotions and dysfunctional coping mechanisms (Beck, 1979; Ellis, 1962). CBT aims to restructure these negative cognitive patterns to promote healthier behaviors and improved mental well-being (Beck, 1993). For substance users, CBT is particularly relevant as it addresses the underlying cognitive distortions that contribute to addiction, while also teaching coping strategies to manage cravings, stress, and emotional triggers (Beck et al., 2011). MI complements CBT by focusing on enhancing motivation, resolving ambivalence, and fostering a collaborative and empathetic therapeutic relationship, encouraging individuals to actively engage in therapy and take ownership of their recovery process (Miller & Rollnick, 2012). In a residential setting, where individuals are immersed in therapy, the integrated use of CBT and MI can have a profound impact on both their mental health and overall life satisfaction by helping them regain control over their thought processes, enhance motivation, and develop healthier coping strategies to manage addiction-related challenges (Carroll, 1998; Hettema et al., 2005). This integrated approach leverages the strengths of both CBT's focus on cognitive restructuring and MI's emphasis on motivational enhancement, creating a synergistic effect that supports sustained behavioral change and improved well-being.

Objectives

- To compare the pre-test mental health scores (depression, anxiety, stress) and life satisfaction between the non-interventional group and the intervention group among substance users.
- To assess the impact of CBT and MI on depression, anxiety, stress and life satisfaction among substance users' post-intervention.
- To examine the effectiveness of CBT and MI in reducing depression, anxiety, and stress while improving life satisfaction from pre-test to post-test among substance users.

Hypotheses

- There was no significant difference in pre-test scores of depression, anxiety, stress, and life satisfaction between the non-interventional group and the interventional group among substance users.
- Post-intervention, the interventional group showed significantly lower levels of depression, anxiety, and stress, and higher life satisfaction compared to the non-interventional group.

- The interventional group led to significant improvements in mental health (decreased depression, anxiety, and stress) and life satisfaction from pre-test to post-test among substance users.

Operational definitions

Mental Health

In this study, mental health includes depression, anxiety, and stress. Depression is marked by low mood, lack of interest, and feelings of guilt, while anxiety involves excessive worry, elevated heart rate, and physical symptoms like dizziness. Stress is defined as events that exceed an individual's coping abilities. These aspects are measured using relevant scale i.e., DASS-21 (Lovibond & Lovibond, 2005).

Satisfaction with Life

Satisfaction with life refers to an individual's subjective evaluation of their overall life quality or specific areas, representing a reliable measure of well-being (Diener et al., 1985).

3. Methodology

Research design

The pre-post experimental research design was used in this study.

Study conditions

The study has 2 groups i.e., non-interventional and interventional group. The interventional group was given 8-10 sessions of CBT and 4 sessions of MI, while residential treatment as usual care was given to the non-interventional group.

Sample

The study involved 60 male substance users (ages 18-40) with 30 in the non-interventional group and 30 in the interventional group from government rehabilitation centers in Mardan, Nowshera, and Malakand, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Participants were selected through convenient sampling, with 20 from each center and then participants were randomly assigned to interventional and non-interventional groups as shown in Figure 1.

Sample Distribution

Figure 1

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The study included male patients admitted for 90-day treatment who had completed 7-10 days of detoxification. Exclusions were patients with psychotic bipolar disorder, those with critical illnesses, and individuals outside the age range of 18-40 years.

Instrument

Demographic Information

The demographics included were groups age, area (rural, urban), drugs currently using (heroin, hashish, Amphetamine (ICE), alcohol, injectables, and multiple drugs).

Cognitive Behavior Therapy

Cognitive behavioral therapy CBT is a form of psychological intervention that is both directive and time limited and is supported by empirical research for handling a host of emotional and behavioral disorders including substance dependence (McHugh et al., 2010). In other words, the CBT as a type of addiction treatment implies understanding and changing the thoughts and behaviors, which push a person to addiction.

Motivational Interviewing (MI)

It is a client-centered approach in which directive techniques are used to activate the motivation of client and his/her commitment to change. This technique helps clients change the uncertainties about change of behavior and aims to support the reinforcing statement that support their reasons for wanting to change and modify their substance abuse behavior (Miller & Rollnick, 2002).

Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS)

The Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS-21) developed by Lovibond and Lovibond (1995) is a 21-item self-report instrument with 4-points scoring (0= did not apply to me at all to 3= applied to me very much or most of the time) used to measure the severity of depression, anxiety, and stress. It consists of three subscales with seven items each.

Reported Cronbach's alpha values for the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress subscales include .72, .77, and .70 (Tran et al., 2013), .92, .90, and .86 (Vignola & Tucci, 2014), and .85, .85, and .87 (Asghari et al., 2008).

Satisfaction with Life Scale

In 1985, an attempt was made to construct a 5-item scale for making global cognitive judgements of one's life satisfaction. Participants have to respond to the questions on a scale ranging from 1 to 7, with 1 being strongly agree and 7 being strongly disagree. The alpha Cronbach reliability was 0.87 (Diener et al., 1985).

Procedure

Three rehabilitation centers i.e., Peshawar, Mardan and Malakand were selected to assess the effect of CBT and MI on depression, anxiety, stress and life satisfaction of drug users. For this purpose, 60 substance users were selected with age ranged 18-40 years and study was conducted in 3-phases. In the first phase, permission was taken from rehabilitation centers, and 20-participants from each center was selected using convenient sampling and were briefed, ensuring voluntary participation and confidentiality. Data was collected using demographic information and various scales, such as the DASS-21 and satisfaction with life scale. In Phase II (Intervention), participants were placed through random sampling into two groups: a non-interventional group receiving usual care and intervention group receiving cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) and motivational interviewing (MI). Phase III (Post-Assessment) involved reassessing participants using the same scales to evaluate the impact of the interventions. The study concluded with a debriefing and gratitude extended to participants and staff.

Data analysis

SPSS-25 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences- 25th Version) was used to analyze data i.e., descriptive statistics for demographics, independent sample t-test for differences between non-interventional and interventional group and paired sample t-test for checking the effect of CBT and MI on mental health and life satisfaction of drug addicts.

4. Results

The results section focused on the impact of CBT and MI on depression, anxiety, stress, and life satisfaction among male substance users. It included pre-test and post-test comparisons between the interventional and non-interventional groups, highlighting changes in mental health outcomes over time. Descriptive statistics, such as means and standard deviations, were provided for both groups, followed by inferential statistics to assess the significance of the findings.

Table 1 Demographic characteristics of study participants (n=60)

Variables	Categories	f	%
Study Groups	Non-interventional	30	50.0
	Interventional Group	30	50.0
Age	Young Adulthood (18-25)	28	46.7
	Middle Adulthood (26-40)	32	53.3
Area	Rural	42	70.0
	Urban	18	30.0
Drugs Currently using	Heroin	12	20.0
	Hashish	4	6.7
	ICE (Amphetamine)	11	18.3
	Alcohol	2	3.3
	Injectables	2	3.3
	Hashish and ICE	14	23.3
	Heroin and ICE	2	3.3
	ICE and Tablets	2	3.3
	Multiple Drugs	11	18.3

Table 1 outlined the demographic characteristics of 60 study participants. Participants were evenly split between the non-interventional and interventional groups. Most were in middle adulthood (53.3%), with the rest in young adulthood (46.7%). A majority (70%) came from rural areas, while 30% were from urban areas. Regarding drug use, the most common substances were heroin (20%), hashish and ICE (23.3%), and multiple drugs (18.3%), with smaller percentages using other drugs like alcohol, injectables, or combinations of substances.

Table 2 Mean Comparison between Pre-Test of non-interventional and interventional Group in terms of Mental Health and satisfaction with life of Substance Users (n=60)

Variables	Non-Interventional		Interventional		p	t(58)	Cohens' d
	M	SD	M	SD			
Depression	15.47	2.14	15.67	2.83	.76	-0.31	.01
Anxiety	15.17	1.95	15.67	2.17	.35	-0.93	.24
Stress	15.03	1.77	15.27	2.49	.67	-0.41	.11
Satisfaction with Life	12.33	1.32	13.37	1.60	.90	-0.72	.22

Note: M= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation

Table 2 revealed that differences between the two groups across all variables (depression, anxiety, stress, and satisfaction with life) were non-significant.

Table 3 Mean Comparison between Post-Test of non-interventional and interventional Group in terms of Mental Health and satisfaction with life of Substance Users (n=60)

Variables	Non- Interventional		Interventional		p	t(58)	Cohens' d
	M	SD	M	SD			
Depression	14.97	2.06	10.43	1.96	.000	8.73	2.25
Anxiety	14.93	2.38	9.93	2.86	.000	7.35	1.90
Stress	15.37	1.96	10.63	2.23	.000	8.76	2.26
Satisfaction with Life	14.53	1.36	19.43	1.98	.000	-11.20	2.88

Note: M= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation

*** $p < .001$

Table 3 showed highly significant differences ($p < 0.001$) across all variables. The interventional group reported significantly lower levels of depression, anxiety, and stress, and significantly higher life satisfaction compared to the non-interventional group. The effect sizes showed strong influence of CBT and MI intervention on depression, stress, anxiety and life satisfaction of study participants.

Table 4 Mean Comparison between Pre-Test and Post-test of interventional group in terms of Mental Health and satisfaction with life of Substance Users (n=30)

Variables	Pre		Post		p	t(29)	Cohens' d
	M	SD	M	SD			
Depression	15.67	2.83	10.43	1.96	.000	9.44	2.15
Anxiety	15.67	2.17	9.93	2.86	.000	13.81	2.26
Stress	15.27	2.49	10.63	2.22	.000	11.85	1.97
Satisfaction with Life	13.37	1.61	19.43	1.98	.000	-11.91	3.36

Note: M= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation

*** $p < .001$

The table 4 showed significant differences and significant improvements in the mental health and life satisfaction of substance users after the intervention. Depression, anxiety, and stress levels all decreased notably from pre-test to post-test, while satisfaction with life increased. The p-values (.000) indicate these changes are statistically significant, and the high Cohen's d values suggest a strong effect.

5. Discussion

The present study aimed to examine the impact of CBT and MI on depression, anxiety, stress, and life satisfaction among substance users. Based on prior research and theoretical foundations, we hypothesized that the CBT and MI intervention would lead to significant improvements in these areas from pre-test to post-test. CBT and MI are widely

regarded as an effective treatment for substance use disorders and co-occurring mental health conditions due to its focus on restructuring negative thought patterns and promoting adaptive coping strategies. In the following discussion, we evaluated the findings of this study in light of previous research and explored the theoretical implications of CBT and MI's effectiveness in improving mental health and well-being among substance users.

Our initial expectations in this study were that the differences in the pre-test scores of the depression, anxiety, stress and life satisfaction between the non-interventional group and the interventional group among the substance users will not be significant. This was supported by the results as the mean comparison of the total variables indicated no significant difference between the two groups. This is in agreement with the studies conducted by Carey et al., 2007 and Wiers et al., 2016 which showed that baseline symptoms of depression and anxiety worth substance user are fairly similar and do not warrant an intervention of substance abuse. These effects may be explained by the fact that many drug-dependent patients present with multiple psychiatric disorders, which leads to similar levels of self-reported distress in various subgroups before treatment (Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration [SAMHSA], 2020). From an empirical perspective, absence of significant differences aligns with the notion that use of substances precipitates specific mental health issues, which then set the level of subjective distress that CBT, MI, and comparable treatment approaches expect to address as the process unfolds (McHugh et al., 2010). This means that any changes in the scores that are obtained after the intervention are most probably as a result of both CBT and MI treatments, thus advocating for the effectiveness of the integrated procedure in tackling the subsequent subjects' cognitive distortions as well as motivational deficiencies.

In addition, it was predicted that there will be a significant reduction in depression, anxiety, and stress and an increase in life satisfaction in the interventional group compared with the non-interventional group after the implementation of the integrated CBT and MI intervention. The results proved this hypothesis, where the analysis in Table 3 indicated significant differences at $p < 0.001$ level, on all the variables. In particular, the integrated CBT/MI group achieved significantly lower levels of depression, anxiety and stress, and significantly higher levels of life satisfaction compared with a non-interventional group; the effect sizes (Cohen's d) were large and positive, suggesting great potential of the combined CBT/MI intervention. These findings are in line with the earlier studies that can include Hofmann et al. (2012) and Cuijpers et al. (2014), which portrayed the usefulness of CBT in enhancing mental health of the patients with substance use disorders and Miller and Rollnick (2012) who described the usefulness of MI in influencing motivation to accept treatment. In theory, the findings sit well with cognitive behavioral and motivational therapies where the goal of CBT is for the participant to challenge his/her negative thought patterns and change the behavioral patterns at the same time MI assists in developing participant's stake in changing injurious self-organization and affect regulation to well-being (Beck, 2011; Miller & Rollnick, 2012). The integrated CBT and MI treatment aims at healing cognitive distortions, imparting coping skills and achieving motivational levels that assist the client in reducing stress, anxiety and depression and enhancing the quality of life of such a client (Beck & Haigh, 2014; Hettema et al., 2005).

Finally, we proposed that, overall, the CBT and MI integrated intervention will improve mental health of substance users, thus reducing depression, anxiety and stress, and increase satisfaction with life from pre-test to post-test. The results confirmed this hypothesis, with decreases on the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale, with corresponding significant, large effect size Cohen *d*, and a significant increase on the Life Satisfaction List, all post-intervention ($p < 0.001$ for all). These findings are similar to the research by Davis et al. (2008), who verified that CBT is effective in the reduction of psychological distress in substance users as it assists individuals in handling negative emotions and other behaviors. Moreover, MI could have played a part to such results by helping participants to get motivated and committed towards the treatment process (Miller & Rollnick, 2012). In the same regard, McHugh et al. (2010), Hofmann et al. (2012) and Hettema et al. (2005) have supported the use of CBT and MI as a powerful combination for the enhancement of mental health among the substance users. In theory, the integrated approach addresses both the maladaptive schemas that underlie the emotional dysregulation; CBT—helps the clients adjust defective scripted thoughts and emotions and develops coping skills; MI—provides the supportive motivational environment that fosters change (Beck, 2011; Wright et al., 2017; Miller & Rollnick, 2012). The use of both approaches is also in concordance with cognitive-behavioral and motivational approaches, where the focus is on changing maladaptive beliefs and overcoming the client's ambivalence as the key processes that account for emotional and behavioral change (Rounsaville et al., 2001; Miller & Rollnick 2012). Besides, Cuijpers and colleagues (2014) reported that CBT not only reduces the symptoms of mental disorders but also improves the quality of life; this can explain why the current study also found a significant improvement of the participants' life satisfaction.

6. Conclusion

The outcome of the study showed that there was a positive effect of the CBT and MI on mental health and life satisfaction of the substance users. In terms of depression, anxiety, stress, and life satisfaction, there was no significant difference between the non-interventional group and interventional group before the test. Nevertheless, the findings of this study after intervention shows the interventional group had significant decreases in depression, anxiety, stress while having significant increases to the life satisfaction when compared to the non-interventional group. The presented results allow to conclude about the efficacy of CBT and MI to enhance the quality of life of substance dependent patients.

7. Limitations & Recommendations

One limitation of the study is the relatively small sample size of 60 participants, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to broader populations of substance users. Additionally, the study focused solely on male participants from specific rehabilitation centers in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, excluding female substance users and those from other regions, which may restrict the applicability of the results to diverse groups. Another limitation is the use of self-report measures, which may introduce bias due to social desirability or inaccurate self-assessment. The lack of long-term follow-up also make it

difficult to assess the lasting effects of CBT and MI on mental health and life satisfaction. Future research should consider larger, more diverse samples, including female participants and individuals from varied socioeconomic and cultural backgrounds. It is also recommended to incorporate longitudinal designs to track the long-term impact of CBT along with other interventions and consider using objective measures alongside self-reports to enhance the reliability of the findings.

8. Implications

Based on the results of this investigation, it is possible to mention crucial and noteworthy implications for substance use treatment and utilization of CBT and MI as an evidence-based intervention targeting mental health and life satisfaction of patients with substance use disorders. The decrease in the level of depression, anxiety, and stress, as well as the increase in life satisfaction, points to the possibility of utilizing CBT and MI in the framework of rehabilitation to support the recovery process. Therefore, the findings outlined here would extend the use of CBT and MI in clinical practice to address the psychological symptomatology along with overall quality of life of individuals in the addiction treatment settings.

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